

Impact of Addressing Education in North-East Nigeria (AENN) Programme on Literacy Education among Children and Youths in Yobe State

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Abstract

Addressing Education in Northeast Nigeria (AENN) programme seeks to respond to the immediate educational needs of youth and children in Yobe state through safe non-formal and formal literacy education in the area of foundational skills (functional, critical and traditional Literacy skills) which is the target area of (AENN) programme. This paper was guided by four research questions which include: to assess the impact of functional, critical and traditional literacy skills provided among children and youth under AENN programme in Yobe state, and last to determine the challenges faced in the implementation of literacy education under AENN programme in Yobe state. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study population was (13123) Children and Youth who registered with AENN literacy education programme. The sample size of 390 was drawn using Krejcie and Morgan Table. Stratified Random sample was used for selecting samples from three programme education zones. The closed questionnaire with liker-type scale was used for data collection. The validation of the instrument was done through content and face validity, by three experts from research unit in Yobe state University. The reliability of the instrument was established through the use of test and retest method, the first week and after two weeks later. The analysis was done using PPMC and result showed a measure of stability at 0.870. The descriptive statistic of simple percentage was used to analyze data collected. The findings of the present study have revealed overall significant impact of functional, critical and traditional literacy skill on social and livelihood among children and youth under AENN programme in Yobe state. It is recommended Based on findings the AENN literacy education programme should continue to satisfy educational need of teaming population in the State.

Keywords: AENN Project, needs of Literacy Education and programme learner-beneficiaries

Introduction

Literacy education is a continuum of learning opportunity provided to learners through non-formal and formal education at various Centers and Institutions by Governments, Individuals, Cooperate bodies and Organizations with aim to extensively, address the public illiteracy and promote literate society (Ekpiwre & Haruna, 2019). In the year (2020) Therefore, the AENN programme in Northeast Nigeria has sought to respond to the immediate Educational needs of 302,500 project beneficiaries between youth school dropout and the out of school children in Borno and Yobe states through safe non-formal and formal education. The project was concerned to ensure that youth school dropout and the out of school children have equitable access to literacy education programme that would focus and foster the skills of functional, critical and traditional literacy skills and provide opportunities through non-formal and formal education programme, in Yobe states as reported in United States Agency for International Development {USAID and AENN Project Manual} (2020).

The critical concern of AENN Project} (2020) is to improve on the social and economic transformation in the life of people in their communities through Literacy skills of functional, critical and traditional literacy skills for the programme learner-beneficiaries around: ability and skill to read, write, spell, listen and speak. Hence the ability and skill of literacy incorporated to the social and economic activities involving the life in the community; reading and writing skills that are adequate to manage daily earns livelihood and employment tasks that require reading skills beyond a basic level; central thinking skills as it is done in both tertiary and secondary education to develop in students.

The literacy skill is also incorporated to health and disease prevention, psychosocial support to prepare youth and children to positive behavior skills, ability and competence for improving social and economic life by providing the learning needs of

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beneficiaries in a consistent manner; maximizing positive gender norms and minimizing negative gender norms in providing equal education opportunities which learner-beneficiaries would have availed themselves under The Literacy education programme for Addressing Education in Northeast Nigeria (AENN) {USAID and AENN Project Manual} (2020)

In spite of the predetermined goals of literacy education programme of (AENN) The recent gradual transformation in public policy, economic policy which have affected community life, social system as well as proliferation in science and technology greatly also affected community way of life in term of security, social, economic and political lives of people in our entire society {USAID and AENN Project Manual} (2020). These circumstances therefore, affect mind-set of many youth school dropout and out of school children to view the impact of literacy education skills to their contemporary life in society and now begin to recognize the needs of literacy skills in order to help them improve and cope with prevailing living gaps in our society. The question to ask here is that, does the Literacy education provided by the AENN programme satisfy the needs of programme beneficiaries in terms of functional, critical, and traditional literacy skills in Yobe state?

Objectives of the study

1. To assess the impact of functional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state.
2. To assess the impact of critical literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state.
3. To assess the impact of traditional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state.
4. To determine the challenges faced in the implementation of literacy education under AENN programme in Yobe state.

Research Questions

1. What are the impact of functional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state?
2. What are the impact of critical literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state?
3. What are the impact of traditional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state?
4. What are the challenges faced in the implementation of literacy education under AENN programme in Yobe state?

Review of Related Literatures

(AENN) Addressing Education in Northeast Nigeria seeks to respond to the immediate Educational needs of 302,500 project beneficiaries between youth school dropout and the out of school children in Borno and Yobe states through safe non-formal and formal education. While laying a foundation for the sustainable improvement of education systems at the community and government levels

AENN in particular has worked with community and government partners to provide safe and certified education opportunities, to revitalize/establish non-formal learning centers and support formal schools in 225 communities. The activity ensured that the safety and well-being of students were prioritized in target locations by engaging communities and school personnel in developing safety plans and codes of conduct for teachers. A minimum package of learning materials was provided to enrolled learners that will improve upon existing curricula to emphasize age-appropriate foundational skills (literacy, numeracy, social-emotional learning, and vocational skills) reported in {USAID and AENN Project} (2020).

AENN project in (2023-2024) identified and established 300 new NFLCs (Non-Formal Learning Center) as revealed {USAID and AENN Project} (2023) in Borno and Yobe States; enrolls 46,385 learners: AENN worked with the CBO (Community-Based Organization) sub-grantees and CCs (Community Coalition). AENN has supported 900 NFLCs and 79 formal schools in intervention communities across Borno and Yobe States. As a result of collective mobilization efforts coordinated by the activity, enrollment figures during the quarter shot up in both States and reached a high of 46,385 (19,599 males; 26,786 females), 29% above the activity's targets of 36,000 basic literacy learners.

In Yobe State AENN Mainstreams 8,445 Basic Literacy completers to formal schools in Yobe States: The activity completed the mainstreaming of all learners from the Year One cohort to either formal school - for learners below the age of 12 or to post-basic literacy programme for adolescent learners. The Yobe States Agency for Mass Education took the lead in the assessment, moderation and certification of learners. AENN also provided testimonials to all learners to certify their participation in the cohort 1 learning activities. After the end of programme examination, the activity collaborated with State Agency for Mass Education (SAME) to compile and send the list of successful learners to SUBEB and LGEAs for placement. In all 8,445

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learners (4,529 males, 3,916 females) were successfully mainstreamed during the reporting period, {USAID and AENN Project} (2020).

Table below shows the number of learners mainstreamed into formal schools and those transitioning into the post-basic literacy program to continue their basic education pursuit along formal and non-formal education streams respectively.

States	Post Literacy			Mainstreamed Into formal Schools		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
Yobe	2,759	1,413	4,172	1,770	2,503	4,273

AENN Year Two Quarter Two Report January 1 to March 31, 2024

Activity Implementation Progress

In Yobe State AENN started the quarter with preparations for the mainstreaming of cohort one learners into formal schools and Post-basic literacy programme, and the enrollment of new learners into cohort 2 Basic-literacy course. The activity worked with relevant government partners to revise and adapt the mainstreaming guidelines first produced by the USAID-Education Crisis Response project in 2017. The new guideline clearly spelt out the pathways for completers of the basic literacy program depending on their age and education experience {USAID and AENN Project} (2024).

As at March 2024, in Yobe State AENN mainstreamed 8,445 cohort one learners (4,529 males, 3,916 females) into formal schools in Yobe States (more learners will be mainstreamed into formal schools as soon as schools reopen). Also among the cohort 1 learners, 8,640 (4,384 males, 4,256 females) adolescent learners transitioned into the Post-literacy program offered by the activity (this number will also increase as more learners transition into the post-literacy course when schools reopen).

Following the Back to Learning campaign conducted in all AENN communities in Yobe States, AENN exceeded its enrollment target for Y2 by 29 per cent. The activity collaborated with the CBOs and CCs for pre- enrollment of the second cohort of learners into the NFLCs in Yobe States.

Table: Number of learners enrolled to Basic and Post Basic literacy program in Yobe States

Learners enrolled into Basic Literacy (cohort 2)			Learners transitioned into Post Basic		
Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
6,070	6,929	12,999	2,759	1,413	4,172

AENN Year Two Quarter Two Report January 1 to March 31, 2024

Concept of Literacy Education

Literacy is the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate and compute, using printed and written materials associated with varying contexts. Literacy involves a continuum of learning in enabling individuals to achieve their goals, to develop their knowledge and potential, and to participate fully in their community and wider society (UNESCO, 2017) as cited in (Kosioma Eli, 2019).

Indabawa (1995) referred to it as the ability to acquire the skills of reading, writing and numeracy in local or foreign language for effective and efficient functioning of individuals in the activities they involve themselves in the society. Thus, literacy is seen as a human right, a tool for personal empowerment and social development as cited in (Christian and Gloria, 2016)

They have further pointed out that the importance of literacy as it was captured by Kaufman and Kraay (2008) that it is the heart of basic Education for All (EFA) and essential for eradicating poverty, reducing child mortality, curbing population growth, achieving gender equality and ensuring sustainable development, peace and democracy.

The Centre for Literacy (2014) put literacy to be a complex set of abilities needed to understand and use the dominant symbol systems of a culture—alphabets, numbers, visual icons—for personal and community development. It touches every aspect of individual and community life. It is an essential foundation for learning through life, and must be valued as a human right.

Canadian Council of Learning (2007) further emphasized literacy to be an essential part of the fabric of modern societies, a thread that links all aspects of life and living in our contemporary world. Its reach is extensive and complex, influencing how fully and effectively a person is able to engage in the social and economic life of his or her community.

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To buttress the above definitions of literacy The National Council of Teachers of English (NCTE, 2008) has summarized what literacy should achieve in today's knowledge economy. According to the Organization's report, active, successful participants in this 21st century global society must be able to; Develop proficiency and fluency with the tools of technology, Build intentional cross-cultural connections and relationships with others so to pose and solve problems collaboratively and strengthen independent thought, Design and share information for global communities to meet a variety of purposes, Manage, analyze, and synthesize multiple streams of simultaneous information, Create, critique, analyze, and evaluate multimedia texts, Attend to the ethical responsibilities required by these complex environments.

Giving credence to this statement, UNESCO (2014) posited the usefulness and benefits of literacy as helping learner to get knowledge and skills that are useful in everyday life activities, helping learners to communicate to people especially in writing, giving the learner a feeling of self-confidence, personal security and freedom from being cheated or exploited. It further helps the individual to actively participate in politics, increases one's economic, political and social gains, and helps the individual to operate new machines (such as the ATM). No wonder, Omoruyi and Omage (2013) noted that the purpose of literacy is the liberation of man from the restraints and limitations of ignorance and dependence. A cursory look at these benefits shows that literacy education programme is capable of raising the consciousness of individual to be more aware of the fundamental problems in their locality and lives, and the extent they are motivated to improve their conditions.

Albert Education also defines literacy as the ability, confidence and willingness to engage with language to acquire, construct and communicate meaning in all aspects of daily living. Literacy is also the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate and compute, using printed and written materials associated with varying contexts. Literacy is also seen a process by which one expands one's knowledge of reading and writing in order to develop one's thinking and learning for the purpose of understanding oneself and the world.

This process is fundamental to achieving competence in every educational system and is required for drop out youth and children survival in a new environment. Basic literacy is an important tool for people to be able to comprehend the world around them and make informed decisions. Literacy is not only a human right but also an enabling tool that will unlock the door to the enjoyment of many other human rights, including the right to freedom of expression, the right to participate in public affairs, the right to work, and the right to participate in cultural life. All these are needed by drop out youth and children to maintain their dignity as human beings. This is cited in (Kosioma Eli, O. 2019)

Literacy is the cornerstone of development. Literacy lifts individuals out of poverty and lacking in basic reading and writing skills is a tremendous disadvantage. Literacy not only enriches an individual's life, but it creates opportunities for people to develop skills that will help them provide for themselves and their family.

From a collective perspective, a literate society is a dynamic society that exchanges ideas, engages in dialogue, innovative and productive. Literacy and English language proficiency are tools that help people move out of poverty and get better-paying jobs to support their families. Limited health literacy is associated with lower health outcomes, increased rates of hospitalization, decreased use of preventative services, poor health management, and higher costs. It is essential for social and human development and provides individual the skills and empowers them to transform their lives with an improved standard of health and ability to earn a higher income. Adhikari and Joshi (2008) as cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014)

In 1991, the US National Literacy Act defined literacy as an individual's ability to read, write and speak in English to solve problems at a level of proficiency necessary to function in society, to achieve one's goals and to develop one's knowledge and potential reported in Eno E. Uduak G. Mbaba, Alice U. and E. Patricia I. (2010) as cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014). Street (2003) defined literacy as conceptions of reading, writing and all types of social practices and many theorists favor such a broad definition in which social contexts of literacy practice are also considered cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014). Warschauer, (2010) asserting that what is considered skillful reading and writing differs with the historical, political and sociocultural contexts as cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014) Gee, (1996) stated that when the context is considered, literacy becomes 'having mastery over the process by means of which culturally significant information is coded.

De Castell and Luke, (1988) as cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014) opined the concept of literacy as a continuum that includes the ability to reproduce letter combinations at one extreme and the ability to engage in logical thinking, higher-order cognitive skills and reasoning on the other as cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014) Clifford, (1984). Lank, shear and Knobel (2004) argued that literacy has many different definitions under varying social conditions and that the nature of the concept changes within the conditions of textual work. Similarly, Leu et al. (2007) argued that achieving a precise definition of literacy is not possible because it's meaning changes regularly. Much of the literacy-related literature of the last decade focuses on what it means to be literate in contemporary society, referring to a spectrum of abilities that relate to digital

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technologies, particularly the Internet. These definitions often attempt to extend the traditional notion of literacy beyond its application to the medium of writing

Forms of literacy Education: Traditional, Functional and Critical Literacy Skills

As the AENN) seeks to respond to the immediate educational needs of children and youth in Borno and Yobe states through safe non-formal and formal education which are incorporated to traditional, functional and critical literacy skills programmes focusing on (literacy; reading, writing, speaking, numeracy, social-emotional learning, and vocational skills) for the sustainable improvement of education systems at the community and government levels.

Traditional literacy skills

In the traditional sense, literacy is the ability of reading and writing. Traditional literacy learning involves learning rules and conventions such as spelling or grammar rules Wilder and Dressman, (2006) as cited in Van Deursen and van Dijk (2014). They have further stated that besides, students read texts seen to be of “literary value” and try to comprehend “meanings” that were thought by the author. Successful acquisition of literacy is manifested by giving the right answers in multiple choice comprehension tests or writing “correctly”, which shows that one has comprehended the “correct” meanings written in texts. Students passively accept the knowledge which is presented to them as “correct”. This approach to literacy, which is called “transmission pedagogy”, produces compliant learners who will be willing to follow directives of received authority at work. In other words, they lack creativity or critical thinking which the modern society requires.

Schrock (2021) opined that traditional literacy skillset contains the traditional literacies of reading, writing, speaking, and listening. Van Deursen and van Dijk (2014) also opined that traditional literacy is the ability to read, write and understand text and is a primary source of information and communication. There is some evidence that one’s capacity to use the Internet remains contingent on his or her level of traditional literacy (Wilder and Dressman, 2006) as cited in van (Deursen and van Dijk 2014).

However, empirical studies focusing on the relationship between traditional literacy and Internet skills among populations at large are, to our knowledge, non-existent. One reason for this lack of empirical investigations might be the overabundance of Internet skills-related concepts and definitions that often remain abstract. Traditionally, literacy has been defined as the ability to use written language actively and passively or the ability to read, write, spell, listen and speak Moats, (2000) and Bawden (2008) states that the simplest form of literacy involves the ability to use language in its written form: ‘A literate person is able to read, write and understand his or her native language and express a simple thought in writing’ this is as cited in van (Deursen and van Dijk 2014)

Functional literacy skills

Functional literacy is seen as the broader concept of literacy however as cited in Oduola (2015) that Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (1997) defines functional literacy as the ability to understand and employ printed information in daily activities at home, at work, and in the community to achieve one’s goals and to develop one’s knowledge and potential. Similarly, Canadian Council of Learning Report (2007) has the following to say about functional literacy a true literacy encompasses much more than just these basic skills. It includes the ability to analyze things, understand general ideas or terms, use symbols in complex ways, apply theories, and perform other necessary life skills including the ability to engage in the social and economic life of the community.

Functional literacy deals with how people actually use such skills to live and work in society. Furthermore, Schlechty (2014) defined functional illiteracy to be ‘reading and writing skills that are inadequate to manage daily living and employment tasks that require reading skills beyond a basic level’. In other words, functional literacy could be seen as the ability of individuals to possess the reading and writing skills that are adequate to manage daily living and employment tasks that require reading skills beyond a basic level. Functional literacy refers to the practical skill set needed to read, write, and do math for real-life purposes, so people can function effectively in their community UNESCO (2000) as cited in Cocchiarella (2018).

Functional approaches to literacy focus on reading and composing the texts that enable students to succeed at school and in society. These approaches aim to help learners understand why real-world texts exist and how this affects texts. Functional approaches start with the question “What is the purpose of this text?” and the next question is “How is the text structured to meet this communicative purpose” This was reported in (Van Deursen and van Dijk 2014).

Critical literacy

Critical literacy is a timeless needed skill that means you are able to analyze and evaluate forms of text by critiquing the author/source and considering the bias that the source has, (Peterson2018). Critical literacy means to be detailed in your thoughts while interpreting a text. It is, “the ability to analyze, evaluate and critically reflect on the media a person encounters and creates” (Buckingham, 2010).

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Critical literacy as cited in the Oxford Research Encyclopedias that individuals must be critically literate not only in school, but we need to take these skills with us through our entire lives and Critical literacy should not be a topic to be covered or a unit to be studied. Instead, it should be looked on as a lens, frame, or perspective for teaching throughout the day, across the curriculum, and perhaps beyond” (Vasquez, 2018). This is a skill that is as necessary as being able to be culturally aware. Just like how you need maps to navigate through winding roads and confusing cities, you need critical literacy to be able to effectively navigate through various texts, in traditional print or in forms of media. He further opined that Critical literacy is a central thinking skill that a tertiary education seeks to develop in students. It involves the questioning and examination of ideas, and requires you to synthesize analyses, interpret, evaluate and respond to the texts you read or listen to.

Batchelor, (2019) has asserted that Critical literacy encourages students to use language to question their everyday world experiences, and in particular, the relationship dynamic between language and power. She further explained that in most cases, these dynamics are rarely obvious. More often, they are part of many nuanced and interconnected factors that underlie the plots and perspectives of the narratives we consume. And unless viewed through a critical lens, the inherent biases that are often present can go unnoticed and unquestioned. “For example,” Batchelor explains, “if you're reading *Little House on the Prairie*, asking students to consider the indigenous voices, and who was there on the Prairie besides the family.”

So critical literacy not only encourages multiple perspectives, it also helps us step back and get a clearer look at a bigger cultural picture. And since she works primarily with education majors studying to become English teachers, Batchelor exposes students to a variety of texts by helping them to re-see the world in numerous ways.

Some of the most commonly used practices that support critical literacy included: reading supplementary texts; reading multiple texts; reading from a resistant perspective; producing counter-texts; having students conduct research about topics of personal interest; and challenging students to take social action.

Reading from a critical perspective requires thinking beyond the text to understand issues such as why the author wrote about a particular topic, wrote from a particular perspective, or chose to include some ideas about the topic and exclude others. Teachers who facilitate the development of critical literacy encourage students to interrogate societal issues and institutions like family, poverty, education, equity, and equality in order to critique the structures that serve as norms, and to demonstrate how these norms are not experienced by all members of society.

By matching our teaching with the specific talents and needs of our students, and by considering our students' points of views in early childhood literacy teaching, we are able to speak to children's identities and empower them. We must use texts in our classrooms with which students will identify, that reflect the lives and experiences of our students, as well validate them. The books we read with our students should address issues that affect the lives of our in important ways.

We must also engage students in meaningful class discussions and conversations about these books, crossing lines of culture, gender, race, and class, as well as providing students with opportunities to critically examine the world around them. Critical literacy does not end in discussion, rather it leads to action.

Critical literacy is a perspective and way of thinking about curriculum, literacies, and the lived experiences of our students. Critical literacy is the ability to read texts in an active, reflective manner in order to better understand power, inequality, and injustice in human relationships. Critical literacy views readers as active participants in the reading process and invites them to move beyond passively accepting the text's message to question, examine, or dispute the power relations that exist between readers and authors. It focuses on issues of power and promotes reflection, transformation, and action (Leo, 2018).

He has also pointed out the important of critical literacy to life as We need critical literacy because it helps us; to establish equal status in the reader-author relationship, to understand the motivation the author had for writing the text and how the author uses the text to make us understand in a particular way, to understand that the author's perspective is not the only perspective, and to become active users of the information in texts to develop independent perspectives, as opposed to being passive reproducers of the ideas in texts.

In addition Critical literacy helps us to read texts in deeper, more meaningful ways, by encouraging readers of all ages to become more actively engaged and use their power to construct understanding and not be used by the text to fulfill the intentions of the author. Critical literacy helps us to move beyond passive acceptance to take an active role in the reader-author relationship by questioning issues such as who wrote the text, what the author wanted us to believe, and what information the author chose to include or exclude in the text. The development of critical literacy skills enables students to look at the world through a critical lens and challenge the power relations within the messages being communicated. Critical teaching allows students to actively work out their learning and problem solving, by providing an outlet, a source of action or social justice.

Critical teaching allows students to better connect classroom practice with the social realms they engage in outside of school, providing a connection between the home, school, and social realms. Critical literacies practice engages students and allowing

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them to use their previous experiences, providing classroom literacies more similar to literacies used outside of the classroom. Using critical literacy as a frame through which the teacher and students design curricula and use literacies in the classroom, helps students view literacy as connected to their personal experiences and as a tool to use effectively to explore and effect change in their lives.

Critical literacy is the form of literacy capability in making contradiction and reflection of the information provided in texts. Critical literacy awareness emphasizes the fact that text can be constructed to understand the background and choices made by the author. By knowing the background, the students will have a comprehensible understanding of a certain text. In critical literacy, this kind of understanding can be received by reading as well as thinking critically which are closely related. This was reported in (Leo, 2018)

She has further examined the relationship between critical literacy and critical reading and thinking can be found in the scheme below. There are sequential stages to create critical literacy skills. The scheme is based on the assumption that receiving information (in this case is reading) and putting them on the brain that involves thinking capability (the ability to think critically) are the basic things to respond the information. In addition, research showed that there was a significant positive relationship between reading and critical thinking; critical reading skills will help students to practice critical thinking.

In order to understand the whole information given, the students will think critically while analyzing and evaluating text in the process of reading. After successfully getting the information, they will take a side and make contradictions for testing the validity of the information, whether it is suitable for the current situation. This is called as critical literacy capability.

Critical reading activity, its process focuses on understanding explicit and implicit information. That critical reading activity helps the students in deeply understanding certain text and criticizing new information. Critical reading techniques involve the ability to analyze, comparing, and assessing the content of the text. This technique requires students to think critically about which they should not only passively receive the information but also actively give responses. It then becomes the basic thing in creating students' critical literacy skills.

Critical thinking is an ability to use complex thinking and reasoning skill. Critical thinking requires the students to be active in analyzing and evaluating the facts of information to obtain or make some conclusion. It can be developed since the early ages in accordance with cognitive development. Its activities are made based on the stages and portion of students' cognitive development through simple and sustainable activities.

Reviewing Impact of Literacy education Programmes of AENN Project in 2024, Yobe state

In March 2024 AENN conducted a Rapid Education and Risk Analysis (RERA) and Gender Equity and Social Inclusion (GESI) assessment to provide conflict, gender, and socially inclusive sensitive recommendations for the program design and operations. The first assessment was in 2018 and focused mostly on understanding the factors responsible for educational exclusion.

In 2020 (AENN) project was introduced aiming to ensure that out of school children and dropout adolescents in Northeast Nigeria have equitable access to literacy education skills opportunities through non-formal and formal education programme.

The Year Two Quarter Report (2024) Assessments shows improved learning performance among cohort one learners: The end-line Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) conducted by the activity showed statistically significant improvements in all reading subtasks (letter sound, syllables, oral reading fluency, and reading comprehension). It also showed statistically significant improvements in almost all Math subtasks (number identification, simple addition, and simple subtraction) girls have higher gains than boys In Yobe, average ORF scores increase by 11 CWPM for males and 14 CWPM for females. Across both states and genders, learners perform best in number identification, then addition, then subtraction.

Yobe States again assess progress made in implementation of the community action plans that were created. The participants were clustered into small groups according to their respective communities to assess and review progress made towards addressing education exclusion within communities. The review session revealed that CCs and community members have continued to make significant progress in the implementation of the community action plans developed and reviewed last quarter. The CCs made presentations showing that community action plan activities, such as community awareness sessions to increase education opportunities for girls and boys, have remained ongoing across the communities.

The (AENN) project work to increase social cohesion by facilitating meaningful community dialogues to ensure that all vulnerable children are part of the non-formal learning communities. Social-emotional learning activities will help different children form positive relationships and peacefully resolve conflicts in NFLCs and formal schools.

The pre-enrollment figures presented earlier in this report shows that the AENN activity is succeeding in bridging the gap between male and female participation in literacy education. Currently, the activity's pre-enrollment figures show disparity between female learners at 58% and that of their male counterparts at 42% in the non-formal learning centers. AENN organized several town hall meetings and back to learning campaigns to encourage the enrollment of girls into either school or non-formal

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learning centers. The findings of the Gender Equality and Social Inclusion (GESI) assessment conducted in 2018 and 2019 showed low level of female involvement in education activities in Yobe States. Based on this finding, AENN prioritized female participation in trainings, workshops and meetings during the reporting period.

AENN also facilitated a training for 250 (142 Male, 105 Female) parents/caregivers on ways of maximizing positive gender norms and minimizing negative gender norms in providing equal education opportunities for girls and boys. The training also enhanced the capacities of the parents/caregivers on ways of preventing, mitigating and responding to school related gender-based violence in a bid to promote violent-free home environment.

The messages of the literacy education was incorporated to provide guidance on simple literacy and numeracy activities that caregivers can conduct with their children at home, along with tips on health and disease prevention, psychosocial support, and caregiver wellbeing. Functional literacy provided increases business reading ability for learners. Functional literacy provided increases business communication ability for learners. Functional literacy provided increases business writing ability for learners.

The training focused on how parents/caregivers can improve their relationship with their children in a continual manner using positive behavior that includes caring, teaching, leading and providing for the needs of a child in a consistent manner.

Challenges associated with literacy education Programme provided by AENN in 2024 Yobe state.

According to the participants highlighted some of the challenges affecting the implementation of literacy education programme were lack of space in classrooms to accommodate new learners. The head teachers said their schools were already overcrowded and that teachers were overwhelmed with the number of learners in their classrooms. To address this challenge, the participants agreed that schools that are yet to start operating double shift systems should do so in order to admit more learners. One of the major challenges was the escalation of the insecurity situation in Northeast Nigeria and effectiveness of Basic Literacy and Post-Literacy Materials Packages. The materials were found to be user-friendly and effective in transmitting the intended contents. However, there is need for language simplification and further contextualization of SEL activities in the Hausa basic Literacy, Numeracy facilitator guide.

Material and Research Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study population was (13123) Children and Youth who registered with AENN literacy education programme. The sample size of 390 was drawn using Krejcie and Morgan Table. Stratified Random sample was used for selection samples from three programme education zones. The closed questionnaire with liker-type scale was used for data collection. The validation of the instrument was done through content and face validity by three experts from research unit in the department of education, Yobe state University. The reliability of the instrument was established through the use of test and retest method, the first week and after two weeks later. The analysis was done using PPMC and result showed a measure of stability at 0.870. The descriptive statistic of simple percentage was used to analyze data collected. The findings of the present study have revealed overall significant impact of functional, critical and traditional literacy skill activities on social and livelihood among children and youth under AENN programme in Yobe state. It is recommended Based on findings the AENN literacy education programme should continue to satisfy educational need of teaming population in the State.

What are the impacts of functional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state?

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	No. sampled	No. of responses	Percentage of responses
1. Functional literacy provided increases business reading ability for learners.	35	83	4	-	130	122	93.85%
2. Functional literacy provided increases business communication ability for learners.	31	87	7	3	130	128	98.5%
3. Functional literacy provided increases business writing ability for learners.	10	24	61	20	130	115	88.5%
Total	76	194	72	23	390	365	280.85%

Source: Field survey, 2024

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Impacts of Functional Literacy Skills

Increases business reading ability for learners as responded 35 (SA) 85 (A) 4 (D) - (SD) with 122 responses at (93.85%)
 increases business communication ability for learners as responded 31 (SA) 87 (A) 7 (D) 3 (SD) with 128 responses at (98.5%)
 increases business writing ability for learners as responded 10 (SA) 24 (A) 61 (D) 20 (SD) with 115 responses at (88.5%)

What are the impacts of critical literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state?

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	No. sampled	No. of responses	Percentage of responses
1. Critical literacy provided enable learners to think over the need of girl child education.	30	71	15	9	130	125	96.15%
2. Critical literacy provided enable learners to distinguish the benefit of health education.	26	79	11	6	130	122	93.85%
3. Critical literacy provided enable learners to estimate benefit of Adult literacy learning.	21	69	19	2	130	111	85.38%
	77	246	45	17	390	358	275.38%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Impacts of critical literacy skills

Critical literacy provided enable learners to think over the need of girl child education as responded 30 (SA) 71 (A) 15 (D) 9 (SD) with 125 responses at 96.15% Critical literacy provided enable learners to distinguish the benefit of health education as responded 26 (SA) 79 (A) 11 (D) 6 (SD) with 122 responses at 93.85% Critical literacy provided enable learners to estimate benefit of Adult literacy learning as responded 21 (SA) 69 (A) 19 (D) 2 (SD) with 111 responses at 85.38%

What are the impacts of traditional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state?

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	No. sampled	No. of responses	Percentage of responses
1. Traditional literacy provided enable learners to read Hausa and English passage.	29	77	11	4	130	121	93.07%
2. Traditional literacy provided enable learners to write Hausa and English passage.	12	57	49	6	130	124	95.4%
3. Traditional literacy provided enable learners to use arithmetic.	14	61	25	23	130	123	94.6%
	55	195	85	33	390	368	283.7

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Impacts of traditional literacy skills

Traditional literacy provided enable learners to read Hausa and English passage as responded 29 (SA) 77 (A) 11 (D) 4 (SD) with 121 responses at 93.07% Traditional literacy provided enable learners to write Hausa and English passage as responded 12 (SA) 57 (A) 49 (D) 6 (SD) with 124 responses at 95.4 % Traditional literacy provided enable learners to use arithmetic as responded 14 (SA) 61 (A) 25 (D) 23 (SD) with 123 responses at 94.6%

Impact of Addressing Educat ... (Saminu & Muhammad, 2024) DOI: <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11475279>

What are the challenges faced in the implementation of literacy education under AENN programme in Yobe state?

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	No. sampled	No. of responses	Percentage of responses
1. Language used for learning slow learners understanding.	12	46	40	15	130	113	86.92%
2. Method used for learning slow learners understanding.	10	29	56	20	130	115	88.46%
3. Location of learning centers and hours used for learning slow learners understanding.	8	17	67	16	130	108	83.07%
	30	92	163	51	390	336	258.45%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Challenges faced in the implementation of literacy education of AENN programme

Language used for learning slow learners understanding as responded 12 (SA) 46 (A) 40 (D) 15 (SD) with 113 responses at 86.92% Method used for learning slow learners understanding as responded 10 (SA) 29 (A) 56 (D) 20 (SD) with 115 responses at 88.46% Location of learning centers and hours used for learning slow learners understanding as responded 8 (SA) 17 (A) 67 (D) 16 (SD) with 108 responses at 83.07%

Discussion of Findings

The impact of literacy education programme to promotion of social and livelihood of people in the World and Nigeria in particular, is the critical area which is much concerned about by many researchers. Despite the challenges faced in the implementation of (AENN 2020 Project) of literacy education programme however there was significant impact in the social and livelihood of people in the Yobe state.

The study shows that Functional literacy provided Increases business reading ability for learners 122 (93.85%) also increases business communication ability for learners 128 at (98.5%) similarly, increases business writing ability for learners 115 at (88.5%). This is in agreement with UNESCO (2000) as cited in Cocchiarella (2018) that Functional literacy refers to the practical skill set needed to read, write, and do math for real-life purposes, so people can function effectively in their community and enable students to succeed at school and in society.

The study shows that Critical literacy provided enable learners to think over the need of girl child education with 125 at 96.15% also Critical literacy provided enable learners to distinguish the benefit of health education with 122 at 93.85% similarly, Critical literacy provided enable learners to estimate benefit of Adult literacy learning with 111 at 85.38%. This is in agreement with Batchelor (2019) that critical literacy not only encourages multiple perspectives, it also helps us step back and get a clearer look at a bigger cultural picture exposes students to a variety of texts by helping them to re-see the world in numerous ways.

The study shows that Traditional literacy provided enable learners to read Hausa and English passage with 121 at 93.07% also Traditional literacy provided enable learners to write Hausa and English passage with 124 at 95.4 % similarly, Traditional literacy provided enable learners to use arithmetic with 123 at 94.6% It is in line with Deursen and van Dijk (2014) stated that the simplest form of literacy involves the ability to use language in its written form. A literate person is able to read, write and understand his or her native language and express a simple thought in writing.

The study shows that Language used for learning slow learners understanding with 113 at 86.92% also Method used for learning slow learners understanding with 115 at 88.46% similarly, Location and space of learning centers and hours used for learning slow learners understanding with 108 at 83.07% . It is in line with report of (AENN 2020 Project) According to the participants highlighted some of the challenges affecting the implementation of literacy education programme were lack of space in classrooms to accommodate new learners.

Conclusion

Empirical evidence from the (AENN 2020 Project) Addressing Education in Northeast Nigeria through literacy education programme has affirmed the endeavor of the (AENN 2020 Project) to meet up the literacy needs of many out of school children and dropout adolescents in Yobe state. This is to help them become critically and functionally literate by preparing them for

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skills abilities and competencies around social and economic or vocational life of the community or to live and work in society, to manage daily living, family, poverty, education, equity, and equality and employment tasks that require reading skills beyond a basic level. The ability to read texts in an active, reflective manner in order to better understand power, inequality, and injustice in human relationships.

Based on the data obtained from the (AENN 2020 Project) highlighted some of the challenges affecting the implementation of literacy education programme in Yobe state. These include the escalation of the insecurity situation, and effectiveness of Basic Literacy and Post-Literacy Materials Packages. The materials were found to be user-friendly and effective in transmitting the intended contents. However, some of the LFs have no prior reading experience in Kanuri and often find it difficult to read. Also, from a technical perspective, there seemed to be inconsistencies in the translations in terms of language usage and orthography.

Despite, the challenges faced in the implementation of the literacy education programme of AENN 2020. The finding of the present study has revealed overall significant impact of functional, critical and traditional literacy skill on social and livelihood of service beneficiaries of the programme in Yobe state.

Recommendation

In response to the above outlined associated challenges affecting the implementation of literacy education programme in Yobe state, it is recommended that the AENN Project should take these steps; to review the SEL books, review of the Kanuri orthographic system relative to AENN Kanuri materials with the view of standardization of orthography and consistent use of common terms in the books through Kanuri Linguists from the University and college of Education, AENN must trains more Master Trainers Learning Facilitators on non-formal Basic Literacy and Post Literacy curriculum. However, there is need for language simplification and further contextualization of SEL activities in the Hausa basic Literacy, Numeracy facilitator guide. In Kanuri Basic Literacy, Numeracy and SEL, it has been observed that generally both the LFs and learners were enthusiastic to use the materials.

In view of the overall significant impact of literacy education programme of the AENN 2020 on social and livelihood improvement. It is recommended the extension of programme to cover the wider communities in the Yobe state.

References

- Adhikari, Y. P., Joshi, U. (2008). Rapid assessment of conflict induced internally displaced persons (IDPs) for their Return resettlement and reintegration. Kathmandu, Nepal: *Nepal Health Research Council*.
- Bawden, D. (2008): *Origins and Concepts of Digital Literacy: Peter Lang, New York*. pp. 17–32. Buckingham, D. (2010). *Beyond Technology: Children's Learning in the Age of Digital Culture*. Cambridge: Polity.
- Canadian Council on Learning (2007) *State of Learning in Canada: No Time for Complacency (Ottawa)*, p. 86. Available at: www.ccl-cca.ca.
- Clifford, G. J. (1984): *Historical Perspectives on Literacy and Schooling*. *Rev. Educ. Res.*, 54, 472–500.
- Cocchiarella C. (2018). *What is Functional Literacy, and Why Does Our High-Tech Society Need It?* December 30, Mindful Technics
- Education (ECPE 2018) *Creating Critical Literacy Skills for Young Learners at Primary School: Titis Angga Rini Elementary School Teacher Education Universitas Negeri Malang Indonesia* angga.rini.fip@um.ac.id
- Ekpiwre, C. & Haruna, A.S. (2019). The nexus between colonialism and the rise of ethnic conflicts in Nigeria: Implication for education and restructuring debate. *Nigerian Journal of Sociology of Education* 13 (2), 353 - 366.
- Eno E. Uduak G. Mbaba, Alice U. and E. Patricia I. (2010) *Literacy in Primary and Secondary Education in Nigeria; Faculty of Education, University of Uyo, and Akwa-Ibom State, Nigeria: In a Journal of Language and Culture Vol. 2(2)*, pp.15-19, February 2011 Available online <http://www.academicjournals.org/JLC> ISSN 2141-6540 ©2011 *Academic Journals*
- Family Health International (FHI 360): *Year Two Quarter Two Report January to March, 2022*.
- Family Health International (FHI 360): *Year Two Quarter Two Report January to March, 2020*.
- Francis O. O. (2015) *Basic and Functional Literacy and the Attainment of Vision 20- 2020 in Nigeria: Developing Country Studies*. www.iiste.org ISSN 2224-607X (Paper) ISSN 2225-0565 (Online) Vol.5, No.14, 2015. Department of Arts Education, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria.
- Gee, J. P. 1996. *Social Linguistics and Literacies: Ideology in Discourses*. London: Routledge.
- Indabawa, S.A. (1995). Literacy and development in the developing world: A critique of the position of the German Adult education association (D.V.V): *Kano Journal of Education Studies (KAJEST)*.

Impact of Addressing Educat ... (Saminu & Muhammad, 2024) DOI: <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11475279>

- Kaufmann, D. and Kraay, A. (2008) Governance indicators where are we? Where should we be going? The global Governance group: *World Bank Institute and the Macro-economics*.
- Kosioma Eli, O. (2019): *Enhancing Internally Displaced Persons, (IDP) Access to Literacy Education Programmes In Nigeria*. Dept. of Arts Education, Faculty of Education, Federal University Otuoke. Bayelsa State
- Language teaching: *Logo International*, 3-20. Tokyo
- Lank shear, C. and Knobel, M. (2004), *Digital Literacy: Concepts, Policies and Practices*, pp. 17–32. Peter Lang, New York.
- Leo, L. (2018) what is critical literacy? *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities: In a Research Journal Social Science (ASSEHRJSS): volume 244*. 1st International Conference on Early Childhood and Primary.
- Leu, D.J. et al. (2007). What is New about the New Literacies of Online Reading Comprehension: *In a journal of National Council of Teachers of English, Urbana, IL*.
- Moats, L. (2000) *Speech to Print: Language Essentials for Teachers*. Paul H. Brookes, Baltimore.
- National Council of Teachers of English {NCTE} (2008) *The NCTE Definition of 21st Century Literacies: An Online Publication of the National Council of Teachers of English*, retrieved from <http://www.ncte.org/positions/statements/21stcentdefinition>.
- Oduola, F. O. (2015) Basic and Functional Literacy and the Attainment of Vision 20- 2020 in Nigeria. Department Of Arts Education, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria: *In a journal of IISTE Developing Country Studies*. Vol.5, No.14, 2015: <http://www.iiste.org/journals/>
- Olori, C. and Gloria O. (2016) *Repositioning Literacy Education Programme for Entrepreneurial Development in Rivers State, Nigeria; Department of Adult Education & Extra-Mural Studies, University of Nigeria, Nsukka and Department of Vocational Education, University of Uyo, Uyo: In a Journal of Educational and Social Research*. MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy Doi:10.5901/jesr.2016.v6n2p177
- Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (1997), *Literacy Skills for the Knowledge Society: Further Results of the International Adult Literacy Survey (Ottawa and Paris)*, p. 14.
- Schlechty, P. C. (2014) "Shaking Up the Schoolhouse: How to Support and Sustain Educational Innovation". *Online Article accessed via www.catdir.loc.gov* (12 th February).
- Schrock, K. (2021). The traditional literacy skillset contains the traditional literacies of reading, writing, speaking, And listening: *Retrieved from Churchill <http://www.slideshare.net/zvezdan/new-literacy-in-the-web-20-world-or-Traditional-Literacy-Kathy-Schrock-Literacy-for-the-Digital-Age> <http://schrockguide.net>*
- Street, B. 2003. "What is 'New' in New Literacy Studies? Critical Approaches to Literacy in Theory and Practice: *Current Issues in Contemporary Education* 5 (2): 77–91
- UNESCO, (2014) *Training manual for facilitators in non-formal education*; Abuja: UNESCO
- UNESCO, (2017) *Defining Literacy: UNESCO Institute for statistics*. <http://uis.unesco.org/>
- United States Agency for International Development {USAID} (2020) *Addressing Education in Northeast Nigeria*;
- United States Agency for International Development {USAID} (2022) *Addressing Education in Northeast Nigeria*;
- United States Agency for International Development {USAID} (2024) *Addressing Education in Northeast Nigeria; Family Health International (FHI 360): Year Two Quarter Two Report January to March, 2024*.
- Van Deursen A.J.A.M. and Van Dijk J.A.G.M. (2014) *Modeling Traditional Literacy, Internet Skills and Internet Usage: An Empirical Study*; Department of Communication Science, University of Twente/Faculty of Behavioural Sciences.
- Van Deursen, A.J.A.M and Van Dijk, J.A.G.M. (2014) *Digital Skills, Unlocking the Information Society: Palgrave Macmillan, New York*.
- Vasquez, V.M. (2018): *Critical Literacy*. Retrieved October 11, 2021, from <http://education.oxfordre.com/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264093.001.0001/acre-fore-9780190264093-e-20>
- Warschauer, M. (2010) *Computer assisted language learning: An introduction*: In Fotos, S. (ed.) *Multimedia*
- Warschauer, M. (2010): *A literacy approach to the digital divide*. Las mulialfabetizaciones en el espacio digital. Ediciones Aljibe, Malaga, Spain.
- Wilder, P. and Dressman, M. (2006) *New Literacies, Enduring Challenges? The Influence of Capital on Adolescent Readers' Internet Practices: Lawrence Erlbaum, Mahwah, NJ* pp. 205